

Cultural Factors in the Epidemiology of Infectious Diseases: A Review

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Medical anthropology is an important field in the social sciences, essential in understanding the aetiology, epidemiology, and treatment of various diseases and ill health conditions, including infectious diseases. A major observation is that research on cultural epidemiology has received little to no attention in the literature of South African biomedical, epidemiological, and medical anthropology fields. However, the present study reviews the literature on the role of gender as a variable of culture in the epidemiology of infectious diseases from a global perspective. The review data presented in this study are derived from searches in PubMed, the World Health Organization Reports, Scopus, and the Web of Science for medical anthropology, public health, epidemiology, cultural epidemiology, and primary health care. The review results show that gender, as a cultural variable, is essential in the epidemiology of infectious diseases. Women's roles and responsibilities in procuring resources for household basic needs and caring for the sick render them vulnerable to infections and, in turn, transmit them to family members, relatives, neighbours, and the wider community. The review provides concrete evidence of how medical anthropology helps define the role of culture in the epidemiology of infectious diseases, which is crucial for public health efforts to comprehend the etiology of epidemics and pandemics, to plan their eradication and treatment. The results of this review can be used to design future exploratory research on cultural epidemiology in South Africa to examine the relationship between culture and infectious disease, to describe the transmission patterns and strategies, and to plan for treatment and response to epidemics and pandemics. The findings of this research could facilitate the development of public health interventions and enhance the adoption of health promotion and protection strategies.

Keywords: Disease epidemiology, infectious disease, health promotion, medical anthropology, culture

The current review is a medical anthropological inquiry into the extent to which gender as a cultural variable could be responsible for the epidemiology of infectious diseases. The main goal is to examine the role of gender roles, viewed as culturally crafted roles and responsibilities, in the causation and distribution of infectious diseases. This area of public health inquiry has received limited attention in scientific research. However, analysis of current medical anthropology and epidemiology research can help understand the relationship between cultural epidemiology and gender, and how gender affects the causes and spread of diseases. The review will identify gaps and encourage areas for further exploratory and descriptive research. Giles-Vernick and Villa (2044) acknowledge that biologists, researchers, public health specialists, and global health institutions have increasingly recognised the contribution of other disciplines, including medical anthropology, to understanding and dealing with epidemics. Anthropologists have long contributed crucial insights into transmission, access to care, treatment, and consequences of endemics and pandemics (Bedford et al., 2019; Calis-Vernick et al., 2019). Kelly et al. (2019) argue that the diverse

insights from medical anthropology were vital in understanding how epidemics work and in creating and applying strategies to enhance preparedness for epidemics, strengthen health systems, and address outbreaks, which played a key role in controlling Ebola in West Africa (Nguyen, 2010).

Epidemiology examines the distribution and determinants of diverse diseases within human populations (Weiss, 2018; Giles-Vernick & Villa, 2024). Epidemiologists, when studying a specific disease, seek to correlate its incidence and distribution with various parameters linked to the most affected individuals to ascertain its likely aetiology (Baker et al., 2022). The primary characteristics analysed encompass age, gender, marital status, occupation, diet, environment, and the behaviour of the patients. These factors are cultural and relevant to the cultural variables considered in medical anthropological studies of disease epidemiology. Cultural epidemiology is an interdisciplinary domain grounded in the principles and methodologies of medical anthropology and traditional epidemiology. It examines local representations of disease and their dissemination (Weiss, 2018).

Infectious disease epidemiology constitutes a subdivision of epidemiology that examines the emergence and transmission of infectious diseases, offering valuable insights about the development and design of intervention methods across many contexts, ranging from households to communities (Ryu et al., 2022). The core of infectious disease epidemiology revolves around the interaction between an infectious agent and its host, the pathways of transmission, and the environmental context of that transmission (Baker et al., 2022; Ryu et al., 2022). Huang et al. (2021) agree that interaction with communities vulnerable and suffering from infections mitigates the spread and impacts of epidemics and

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pandemics. Public health authorities frequently assess the intensity and condition of epidemics by engaging with the affected communities to assess and devise the means to prevent their transmissibility (Qi et al., 2021; Baker et al., 2022).

Prior research conducted in other parts of the world has greatly enhanced comprehension of the relationship between socio-cultural characteristics and infectious diseases. For instance, social class, economic status, gender, and cultural attitudes and practices correlate with the occurrence and distribution of infectious diseases (Ryu et al., 2022). Achangwa et al. (2022) concede that pathogens induce infectious diseases that can propagate directly between persons or indirectly via a vector or the environment. Consequently, experts classify them as communicable diseases, since their transmission depends on contact among individuals within a population (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). The transmission of infectious diseases contrasts with that of non-communicable diseases, as the acquisition of an infectious disease is contingent upon its prevalence among the community.

Method

Infectious disease epidemiology studies are designed and conducted from the medical sciences' perspective. Such studies are often conducted through the integration of syndromic, virological, and digital data acquired from epidemic investigations, continuous surveillance, and seroprevalence surveys to enhance understanding of the epidemiology of infectious diseases. This review employed medical anthropological methodologies and principles to elucidate cultural variables influencing the transmission of infectious diseases. The objective of the review is to assess the degree to which gender, as a cultural component, may influence the spread of infectious diseases at the household level. The study draws its data from multiple literature sources. The search was conducted through key electronic scientific databases, such as PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, SpringerLink, ResearchGate, EBSCOhost, ProQuest, Science Direct, Elsevier, and BioMed Central. Additional literature sources comprised published papers, book chapters, dissertations, and theses.

Results and Discussion

Infectious Diseases

Infections have increasingly emerged as persistent global problems to public health (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Infectious diseases endemic to South Africa encompasses, but are not confined to, influenza, malaria, cough, pertussis, measles, dengue fever, smallpox, cholera, bacterial diarrhoea, hepatitis A, typhoid fever, oral infections, diabetes mellitus, gastrointestinal infections, and tuberculosis (Statistics South Africa, 2017; Schwartz et al., 2019). Bih et al. (2023) indicate that South Africa experiences a heightened infectious illness burden, resulting in a greater percentage of fatalities. The government aspires to reduce the prevalence of infectious diseases. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) indicates that numerous member states have established initiatives to reduce the prevalence of infectious illnesses. These encompass minimal national requirements for the efficient management and prevention of infections by broadening the national response to infections through the engagement of all societal sectors and stakeholders to mitigate new illnesses and their effects on individuals, families, and communities.

In South Africa, there is scant literature regarding the epidemiological models employed to assess the dissemination of infectious illnesses for their management and control. The literature mostly emphasises the characterisation of epidemics and pandemics; however, the relationship between culture, human behaviour, practices, and the dissemination and response to illnesses remains underexplored. The social dimensions of infectious disease transmission are essential to comprehend the nature, etiology, dissemination, and response to epidemics and pandemics. This is a medical anthropology approach that illustrates the relationship between socio-cultural variables and the etiology, epidemiology, and treatment of infectious diseases. The method is supported by analyses of the literature about the role of gender in the epidemiology of infectious diseases in the subsequent sections next sections of this review.

Gender and Infectious Disease Epidemiology

The transmission of infectious diseases is contingent upon the number of vulnerable individuals within the community and their effective interactions. Gender is recognised as a significant mode of transmission. Unlike non-communicable diseases, one infected individual (case) can serve as an initial source for subsequent infections, resulting in transmission chains within a population. In infectious disease epidemiology, the examination of human interaction patterns is crucial. The World Health Organization (2021) delineates the transmission of infectious disease through a chain of essential factors required for infection and disease manifestation in an individual. These include gender norms, roles, relations, and concerns of gender inequality and unfairness profoundly affect individuals' health. These pathways can generate variations in individuals' vulnerability to disease and its advancement. For Magnus et al. (2004) gender norms affect differences in disease-related risks between men and women, as well as in the management, treatment, and transmission of infectious diseases to family members as they adhere to their cultural obligations and roles. Gender norms, upbringing, societal roles, disparities in power, and resource accessibility contribute to differences in individuals' susceptibility to illness, their experiences of disease, health behaviours (such as seeking care), and their access to and utilisation of health services, treatment responses, and health outcomes (Nkangu et al., 2017). de Vasconcelos et al. (2018) acknowledge that gender may influence an individual's experiences in crises and emergencies, their vulnerability to diseases, and their access to healthcare, water, hygiene, and sanitation.

Household Chores: Gender norms delineate the assigned duties and obligations for men and women within a community. In nearly all countries, women dedicate more time to domestic activities than men, potentially exposing themselves to pathogens present within or near the residence daily. Also, women encounter infections while performing domestic extramural activities, such as laundering or collecting water and firewood. The World Health Organization (2021) recognises that the three primary elements of gender norms, duties and responsibilities, decision-making authority, and resource accessibility render women more susceptible to infections and position them as significant transmitters of infectious diseases. These factors, in turn, delineate the behaviours of men and women, their access to and control over resources, and their agency regarding decision-making and mobility. Moreover, these cultural characteristics influence disparities in the risks associated with

diseases between genders, in addition to care, treatment, and the impacts of disease (WHO, 2022).

Nkangu et al. (2017) assert that in many communities, gender-discriminatory practices position women in inferior roles within domestic and societal contexts, thereby heightening their infection risks and imposing further obstacles to accessing essential resources. Gender directly affects the three fundamental components of the spread model: susceptibility, exposure to pathogens, and reaction to sickness (Buckee et al., 2021). According to Nkangu et al. (2017), and Tamayo and Parda (2023), gender elucidates the distinct roles of men and women in domestic, communal, and societal contexts, influencing their susceptibility to disease vectors and facilitating opportunities for effective prevention, control, and management of these diseases.

The primary mode of transmission of infectious diseases among households is by direct contact (Nkosi et al., 2021). In many impoverished nations, women often dedicate hours to laundering garments while standing in contaminated waters, thereby exposing themselves to waterborne illnesses such as schistosomiasis (Michelson, 1993; WHO, 1998; 2010a), which are often categorised as infections as a result of person-to-person transmission (WHO, 2023). Transmission at the household level typically happens through direct contact with airborne respiratory droplets that swiftly disseminate when an infected individual coughs or sneezes (WHO, 2021). Giesecke (1994) recognises that a fundamental idea of epidemiology is an individual's exposure to a potential pathogenic agent or substance, typically through contact, kissing, breastfeeding, airborne transmission, short-range droplet transmission, coughing, and sneezing. This route of transmission is the initial point from which the infection passes to a person. Buckee et al. (2021) acknowledge that in directly transmitted illnesses, the origin is an infected individual. Mothers and daughters, serving as carers, may transmit infections to other family members while fulfilling their roles and responsibilities, such as bathing, washing, and sharing beds and food with ailing relatives (Buckee et al., 2021).

Caring for Sick Family Members: Women are more predisposed than men to assume caregiving roles for the ill. In this position, women are exposed to infectious pathogens than men. This distinction is crucial for diseases such as Ebola haemorrhagic fever and SARS, which are transmitted through close contact (Anker, 1998). The United Nations Development Group (2015) and Minor (2017) confirm that these characteristics elevated the risk of infection for women and girls compared to men during the Ebola pandemic of 2014-16 in Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone. The WHO (2022) supports that in most contexts, women are expected to serve as the principal carers for ill family members. Providing care for the ill increases the risk of exposure, especially for diseases that transmit directly between individuals (WHO, 2023). The WHO (2021) asserts that susceptibility to illnesses necessitates exposure to the pathogen for certain individuals, with a subset of those exposed subsequently developing illness. Women close to ill family members are vulnerable to communicable diseases (Buckee et al., 2021). For example, caring for ill family members constituted a substantial risk factor for outbreaks of the Nipah virus and Ebola, both of which are transmitted through direct contact (WHO, 2021). According to Nkangu et al. (2017), this mode of disease transmission is particularly problematic when caring for young toddlers entails intimate interaction and fosters opportunities for exposure during the child's infectious period, leading to a higher incidence of disease

among caretakers. Similarly, women may have an increased risk of infection during illness outbreaks compared to men, as they represent most frontline healthcare professionals (WHO, 2021).

Mobility: Men and women generally participate in distinct activities, frequently occurring in varied locations and with various social contacts, resulting in disparate exposures (Buckee et al., 2021). Interactions with other people take place at locations where the women should collect resources, such as water and food for household consumption. This behaviour has facilitated the spread of malaria, especially when women participate in cyclical migration characterised by leaving their location and subsequently returning to obtain essential household necessities (WHO, 2022). The women's numerous responsibilities, including laundering, collecting water, and tending to children and ill relatives, expose them to diseases and the risk of transmission to other family members (Nkangu et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The essence of infectious disease epidemiology centres on the interplay between an infectious agent and its host, the modes of transmission, and the environmental context around that transmission. This review provides evidence regarding the influence of culture on the transmission of infectious diseases. The study demonstrates a correlation between gender and the epidemiology of infectious diseases. The adherence to gender-specific roles and obligations increases women's susceptibility to infectious diseases, subsequently spreading these infections to family members, neighbours, or others with whom they interact. The review findings have relevance to the reproductive number R_0 for infectious diseases, quantified as the number of novel infections produced by one sick individual within a completely susceptible population, as elucidated by Grassly and Fraser (2006). This review highlights deficiencies in the consideration of culture within studies on infectious disease epidemiology. The review suggests that incorporating medical anthropologists in descriptive studies of infectious disease epidemiology may enhance understanding of the aetiology, transmissibility, and treatment of epidemics and pandemics, an essential element of health promotion.

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